

Short Communication

Experiential Evolution from both Awakening and Dreaming

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Since the beginning of human time in this world, the only thing which is found constant is the change in human behavior throughout ages. The gradual change, or in more liberal senses, advancement in human form of both physiological and psychological is called evolution of human race. As humans evolved throughout millions of years uptil now, the behavior, ethics, lifestyle and thought processing have found being enhanced and a wide range of capabilities have been developed in human. In material sciences, there are two aspects of grasping the concept of evolution. One being the Darwinian Theory of Evolution in which he mentioned that all species biologically evolved throughout time from one single gene and from natural inheritance, the form changed gradually to different species and as he says, the purpose of "war of nature" is the production of higher animals (C. Darwin, 1872). The other which supports this theory and the rest states that evolution is a process in which the species gained intelligence throughout experiences to shape itself in the most saturated and balanced form, and thus human. Both of the definitions covers one aspect of reality which endorses that evolution is a continuous process which does not stop at any given point of time. Let us review the evolution of human species in general. A human mind is a combination of conscious, unconscious, subconscious, and super conscious in some cases. In general, a person is observed to evolve in one aspect, i.e. while he/she is awake and experiencing everything that happens around him/her, while the aspect of sleep is undervalued or in other words, neglected. When a person is asleep, he/she is more closely linked to his/her subconscious which plays the most important part in evolution. When a person observes something in consciousness, it is firstly related to the relevant observation predisposed in his/her subconscious, if it is found in favor, the observation is strengthened, if not, it is yet saved in subconscious to reappear in conscious as another observation for confirmation. For example, when a child learns $2+2=4$ for the first time, the observation of this calculation is saved in the subconscious as a raw form which later on is strengthened and confirmed when the child relearns it at home and thus it becomes a fact for the child which in future expands the child's learning process for advanced mathematics based on these predisposed facts of early age.

How does this mechanism work in dreams? In order to understand this, one must be clear to the point that

dreaming is a process in which the physiological aspects of the body and its psychological responses by the brain are stored in a part of the brain called subconscious (W. Hassan 2014). A dream is a tool of mind through which the experiential learning throughout time is racked in its place in one's subconscious, in other words, a dream is a way of assuring the experiences subconsciously to maintain a state of conscious when the person wakes up. Now as the subconscious of a person is maintained, evolved and expanded by dreams, the consciousness of a person is also evolved by enhancing the ability to attain more experiences and to think from a broader point of view. And if by looking closely, it will appear to be true that the ability to perceive and application of broader thought processing have helped human race from dying of fever to surviving of heart transplant. How do thoughts and perceptions help in physiological manner?

"When we imagine something, we actually cause it to become reality".

Since thoughts and perceptions are purely psychological aspects of human being, it is both linked and disconnected from the physical changes occurring in a person, subject to the transformation of thought requirement in materialism. For example, the thought of human race to fly in the skies was generated in 400BC in China (K. Dalamagkidis et al, 2012) by the discovery of kite which could fly in the air and that made humans think about flying in the skies while it was made possible for the first time perfectly in 1905 AD by Wright Brothers in Ohio, USA. In this manner, the evolutionary process of aero planes started from a thought in 400BC and had put its first foot of success in physical reality after 2341 years in 1905 AD. One question which arises in this evolution is the process of forgetting dreams frequently and is thought to be useless. It is to be noted that the difference between dreaming and waking up is the access of the information in subconscious. When a person is awakened, he/she is able to access only such parts of his/her subconscious which is required by the consciousness at a given point of situation. Similarly, when a person is asleep and dreaming, he/she accesses the subconscious at a wider angle than being in conscious. By this manner, the importance of accessing subconscious thoroughly while being in

conscious is a bigger step in order to evolve the physical changes of a human.

Recent researches about human evolution through thoughts include an important work by Cecelia Heyes in her research " New Thinking: The evolution of human cognition" in which she mentions the importance of thought generation processes which triggered human mind to develop the abilities to invent languages, culture, technology and other aspects. In her research, she mentions that humans are species that specialize in thinking and knowing and the extraordinary cognitive powers as compared to the rest of the species have enabled humans to evolve in every manner, from eating habits to building houses, transportation of bodies in various locations in short interval of time, and transferring of mind in remote places by telescope and electron microscopes (C. Heyes, 2012). Another study by Erin Weyman suggest that humans, when not been able to invent languages, used drawings to convey their messages between people, as drawings are a way to interpret messages which one is unable to explain in vocabulary, if there is any.

Conclusion

Evolution is a continuous process. One can neither confine it in a specific direction, nor it is desirable to put an end to it since it is the quality of a human mind to explore endlessly and to gain intelligence at it's finest. Dreaming itself is a part of human evolution which helps one to attain a stress free life as most of the exertions of one's emotions are carried in dreams subconsciously in order to soothe the state of mind where required. Food for thought, the evolutionary process does not end with human beings only, it is working from cell to universal level if observed correctly.

References

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